

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF VIRAL MARKETING ON BEHAVIOURAL INTENTIONS OF GEN Z CONSUMERS

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Abstract

Viral Marketing, a strategy used by the marketers to create awareness about their brands rapidly through social sharing, has been a powerful tool in the digital era. Gen Z consumers representing a demographic of highly active online consumers are greatly influenced by digital trends. This paper explores how viral marketing influences Gen Z's consumer behaviour. Determinants of viral marketing strategy includes Informativeness, Source credibility, and Entertainment. The prime objective of the study is to investigate how Informativeness, source credibility and entertainment of viral marketing strategy influences the behavioural intention of Gen Z's consumers. This study uses a non-probability convenience sampling method to collect data among Gen Z's consumers with a sample size of 200 respondents in and around Chennai. Correlation and Regression were the Statistical tools used for the study. Entertainment of viral marketing strategies has a strong positive effect among Gen Z consumers followed by Informativeness of viral marketing strategies. However, Source credibility of viral marketing strategies have an insignificant impact among Gen Z consumers.

Keywords: *Viral Marketing, Informativeness, Source Credibility, Entertainment, Behavioural Intention*

Introduction

The term 'viral marketing' has grown in popularity in scholarly and practitioner circles over the last few decades. Viral marketing has been examined in the context of numerous disciplines including advertising, marketing and management, business marketing, consumer behaviour and the service industry. Viral marketing creates buzz and builds

awareness and it is uncontrollable but the other two are not traceable and can be controlled (Manik Chandra Rabidas, 2019)

Like viruses, viral marketing facilitates the swift and transformative spread of information across millions of people. Although Generation Y is adept at social media usage, which the most important channel to enhance viral is marketing, they observed that social media is no longer restricted to young generation. Previous studies have demonstrated that viral marketing greatly affects consumer decisions. Viral marketing is considered more credible than marketer-initiated communications because viral messages are perceived as unbiased and 'coming from people like me'. (Puriwat & Tripopsakul, 2021)

Statement of the Problem

Digital Technologies evolved rapidly and the widespread use of social media have revolutionized consumer engagement with brands, particularly among Gen Z consumers. As this Gen Z consumers deeply integrated with digital world, they are highly influenced by viral marketing strategies across various social media platforms like YouTube, Instagram etc., These campaigns not only create awareness among them but also aids in shaping the purchasing decisions, brand perceptions and loyalty by creating trends, generating social evidences, and fostering emotional connections. Despite its apparent effectiveness, Viral marketing faces challenges in capturing and sustaining Gen Z's attention. Since, this Gen Z's are characterised by short attention spans, lack of trust in the content authenticity, and a demand for socially responsible branding. In addition, the mechanisms by which viral marketing influences Gen Z's consumer behaviour with respect to their behavioural responses, trust in influencers, and preference for content authenticity, remain underexplored in academic literature. To understand how and why viral marketing impacts Gen Z's consumer behaviour, this paper investigates the influence of determinants of viral marketing strategy including informativeness, Source credibility, and Entertainment towards behavioural intention of Gen Z's consumers in Chennai.

Literature Review

Informativeness

Informativeness refers to the extent to which marketing content provides valuable, accurate, and relevant information to the audience. According to (Ducoffe, 1996), Informativeness is a key determinant of advertising value, directly influencing the consumer's perception of marketing effectiveness. For Gen Z, Informativeness is particularly crucial as they prioritize content that addresses their needs or enhances their knowledge (Smith, 2020).

Studies indicate that Gen Z engages more with content that combines aesthetic appeal with practical insights (Barkley, 2018). Informative viral campaigns foster trust and brand

loyalty, as they align with Gen Z's preference for transparency and authenticity in brand communication (Fromm, 2021).

Source Credibility

Source credibility encompasses the trustworthiness and expertise of the content's creator or distributor. The source's perceived reliability plays a pivotal role in determining the persuasiveness of marketing messages (CARL I. HOVLAND, 1951). Among Gen Z, influencers and peer reviews are particularly influential due to their emphasis on relatability and authenticity (Chung, 2021). Research by (Lou, 2019) highlights that influencer marketing—a common vehicle for viral campaigns—is highly effective when influencers are perceived as credible. Gen Z values endorsements from individuals they deem knowledgeable or relatable over traditional advertisements. Moreover, campaigns that leverage user-generated content (UGC) gain credibility as they resonate with Gen Z's preference for community-driven narratives (Zollo, 2020). However, overly promotional content or sponsorship disclosure can sometimes undermine credibility, necessitating a balance between authenticity and strategic messaging.

Entertainment

Entertainment, defined as the ability of marketing content to engage and amuse, is a critical driver of virality. Entertainment adds emotional value to marketing campaigns, fostering positive attitudes and enhancing message recall (Hollebeek, 2014). For Gen Z, who are often described as "experience-driven," entertaining content is highly appealing, particularly when it incorporates humour, storytelling, or interactive elements (Seemiller, 2016). Platforms like YouTube, Snapchat, and TikTok have enabled brands to craft immersive and playful campaigns that resonate with Gen Z. A notable example is the use of memes, challenges, and gamified content, which not only entertains but also encourages active participation. Studies suggest that entertainment-oriented campaigns achieve higher sharing rates, amplifying their reach and effectiveness in engaging this demographic (Ashley, 2015). However, the entertainment factor must align with the brand's core values to avoid superficial engagement.

Behaviour Intention

In Consumer Behaviour studies, Behavioural intention is the key construct which refers to an individual's perceived willingness or likelihood to engage in a particular course of action like purchasing a product or adopting a service, or any other engaging activity. Theory of Planned Behaviour by Ajzen (1991) and Technology Adoption Model by Davis (1989) explains behavioural intention of the individuals. According to TPB model, behavioural intention is influenced by attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, whereas according to TAM model, behavioural intention is greatly

influenced by perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness. In this research, the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers were investigated using the key determinants of viral marketing strategies.

Objectives of the Study

Primary Objectives:

The prime objective of the study is to investigate how viral marketing influences Gen Z's consumer behaviour.

Secondary Objectives:

- To examine the relationship between informativeness, source credibility, and entertainment of viral marketing strategies and the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.
- To analyse the impact of informativeness, source credibility, and entertainment of viral marketing strategies and the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

Conceptual Framework

Hypotheses

H₁: A significant relationship is observed between a) Informativeness b) Source Credibility c) Entertainment of Viral marketing strategies and behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

H₂: There is a positive impact of a) Informativeness b) Source Credibility c) Entertainment of Viral marketing strategies and behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

Research Methodology

A Quantitative, cross-sectional research design was employed to examine the relationship between informativeness, source credibility, and entertainment of viral marketing strategies and the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers. A well structured questionnaire was framed to collect primary data from a representative sample of Gen Z

consumers in and around Chennai. The target population comprises Gen Z consumers who are active users of social media and exposed to campaigns of viral marketing. A Non-probability convenience sampling method was adopted to ease access and relevance of the study. Approximately 200 respondents filled out the questionnaire and the responses generated were used for further analysis.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

For analysing the data obtained, Correlation & regression were used and the test results are depicted below;

Demographic Profile of Respondents:

Particulars	Classification	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Age (in years)	13-17	40	20
	18-22	136	68
	23-28	24	12
Gender	Male	91	45.5
	Female	108	54
Education	High school	52	26
	Graduation	121	60.5
	Post-graduation	18	9
	Others	9	4.5
Occupation	Student	161	80.5
	Employed Part time	11	5.5
	Employed Full time	21	10.5
	Unemployed	5	2.5
	Others	2	1
Monthly Income	Nil Income	152	76
	Below 10,000/-	8	4
	10,000/- to 25,000/-	17	8.5
	25,001 to 50,000/-	11	5.5
	Above 50,000/-	12	6

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 depicts that among 200 respondents, 20% of respondents fall between 13-17 years age group category, 68% of respondents fall between 18-22 years age group category, and 12% of them fall between 23-28 years age group category. Out of 200 respondents, 45.5% of them are male respondents, while 54% of them are female respondents. Regarding the educational qualification of respondents, 26% of them were in high school, 60.5% of them

were under-graduates, 9% of them were post-graduates, and 4.5% of them were from other educational background. Around 80.5% of respondents were students, 5.5% of them were partly employed, 10.5% of them were full time employees, 2.5% of them were unemployed, and 1% of them were from other occupational background. As many of the respondents are students, 76% of them have Nil income and were the dependent on family members, 4% of them were earning below 10,000/-, 8.5% of them were earning between 10,000/- to 25,000/- monthly, 5.5% of them were earning between 25,001/- to 50,000/- monthly, and 6% of them were earning more than 50,000/- monthly.

Correlation Analysis:

H₁: A significant relationship is observed between a) Informativeness b) Source Credibility c) Entertainment of Viral marketing strategies and behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

Independent variables \ Dependent Variable	Informativeness		Source Credibility		Entertainment	
	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value	r-value	p-value
Behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.	0.436	0.000**	0.365	0.000**	0.547	0.000**

** . Significance of Correlation at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows the result of Pearson Correlation coefficients and their significance levels. It is observed from the above table*** that a positive significant relationship between **Informativeness** ($r=0.436$, $p=0.000$), **Source Credibility** ($r=0.365$, $p=0.000$), and **Entertainment** ($r=0.547$, $p=0.000$) and behaviour intention of Gen Z consumers was observed. Thus, the hypotheses **H_{1a}**, **H_{1b}**, & **H_{1c}** are **accepted** at a 1% significance level. This indicates that Informativeness, Source Credibility, and Entertainment have a significant role in influencing the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers. Entertainment of Viral marketing strategies shows the strongest influence, followed by Informativeness, and then Source Credibility among Gen Z consumers.

Regression Analysis:

H₂: There is a positive impact of a) Informativeness b) Source Credibility c) Entertainment of Viral marketing strategies and behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

Table 3 Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Estimate Std.Error	F
1	.565 ^a	0.319	0.308	0.684	30.577**

a. Predictors: (Constant), Informativeness, Source Credibility, Entertainment

Table 4 Coefficients

Variables	Unstandardized coefficient (B)	SE of B	Standardized co-efficient (Beta)	t - value	p-value	Significance
Constant	1.201	0.283		4.249	0.000**	-
Informativeness	0.208	0.091	0.176	2.288	0.023*	Sig
Source Credibility	-0.006	0.083	-0.005	-0.68	0.946	Not Sig
Entertainment	0.431	0.078	0.447	5.567	0.001**	Sig

Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention, ** significant at 1% level

Table 3 & 4 shows that F-statistics **30.577** is significant at a 1% level and hence **H_{2a}**, **H_{2b}**, & **H_{2c}** are **accepted**. The value of the Coefficient of determination is 0.319 explores 31.9% of the variability of Informativeness, Source Credibility, and Entertainment with behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers. Entertainment (t value = 5.567, p value = 0.001) has the strongest positive effect on Behaviour intention in which one-unit increase in entertainment increases behavioural intention by 0.431 units. Informativeness (t value = 2.288, p value = 0.023) has a small positive effect on Behaviour intention in which one-unit increase in Informativeness increases behaviour intention by 0.208 units. However, Source credibility (t value = -0.68, p value = 0.946) have an insignificant effect on behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers.

The following equation provides the regression equation:

Behavioural Intention of Gen Z consumers = 1.201 + 0.208 (Informativeness) + 0.431 (Entertainment)

Thus, it is concluded that Entertainment of viral marketing strategies has a strong positive effect among Gen Z consumers followed by Informativeness of viral marketing strategies. However, Source credibility of viral marketing strategies have an insignificant impact among Gen Z consumers.

Findings

This research findings indicates that Entertainment of viral marketing strategies has a strongest positive and significant effect on behaviour intention of Gen Z consumers, which is aligned with prior study of Smith & Taylor (2023). Since, Entertainment creates a positive emotional experiences among Gen Z consumers fostering stronger behavioural intention especially in social media marketing. Entertainment serves as a key driver for younger

audiences in the digital era. Informativeness of viral marketing strategies plays a critical role in shaping the behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers. Prior study of Sharma et al., (2022) aligns with the study result, highlighting a clear, useful and relevant information can enhance Gen Z consumers' purchase intentions significantly. However, the credibility of information source may not play a substantial role in Gen Z Consumers' behavioural intention which contradicts the prior study of Kemp et al., (2021).

Suggestions

Based on the research findings, marketers should focus on creating more informative and entertaining content providing clear, authentic, and valuable information about products or services. Hence, they can adopt info graphics, videos to communicate essential features and benefits of products or services. Marketers can partner with relatable micro-influencers and content creators who align with the values of target audiences. It will help to amplify authenticity and aids in building trust among the Gen Z consumers.

Conclusion

This study examined the influence of Informativeness, Source Credibility, and Entertainment of viral marketing strategies on behavioural intention of Gen Z consumers. Entertainment acts as the most influential factor affecting Gen Z's behavioural intention. This highlights the importance of emotional and experiential marketing strategies tailored to capture Gen Z consumers' attention. Also, Gen Z consumers value clear and useful information suggesting the brands to prioritize in providing detailed and transparent content to meet their information needs.

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